

The Promotional Mix in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel Is Between Reality and Ambition

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the reality of the promotional mix in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel. The study adopted the descriptive analytical approach, and the study population consisted of 1000 of the company's customers in the Sinai and Suez Canal regions. A random sampling method was used, and the sample size was 278 individuals, and data was collected through A structured questionnaire was prepared for this purpose. The results of the study showed that the advertising field got a high degree with a relative weight (68.3%). The field of personal selling got a high degree with a relative weight (69.86%), and the field of sales activation got a high degree with a relative weight (76.86%), while the field of publicity and publication got a high degree with a relative weight (78.64%). The study recommended the necessity of enhancing the concept of the promotional mix with its various elements (advertising, personal selling, sales activation, advertising and publishing), monitoring and directing companies that have been privatized to enhance the concept of promotional mix among their customers.

Keywords: Promotional mix, Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel, Egypt.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most of the marketing studies aimed to identify the consumer, his needs and desires in an attempt to provide the goods and services that suit him, and the possibility of distinction and diversity in them, and to influence his behavior and interests through the process of the marketing mix, and to identify the methods of the promotional mix, which are the most effective and efficient in influencing his behavior and purchasing decisions (James M., C, 1995)

Statistics confirm that 40% of customers face problems worth complaining once they have finished purchasing the good or service, and most of these customers turn to competing companies if the reasons for their complaints are not resolved by the organization (Rashad, 2012, P: 11).

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The promotional mix affects the consumer's awareness, desires and choices. Therefore, choosing the appropriate promotional means is more important in reaching the target customers at a lower cost and more effective, using the promotional mix with its various elements (advertising, personal selling, publicity and publication, sales activation).

The problem of the study is represented in the following main question:

What is the reality of the promotional mix in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel?

3. THE SURVEY

1. **About The Company:** Al-Ezz Steel Reinforcing Company (Egyptian joint stock Company) was established in accordance with the provisions of Law No. 159 of 1981 and the company was registered in the

Commercial Register under No. 472 of Menoufia Governorate on 2/4/1994. 1994 based in Sadat City. It is a subsidiary of Ezz Group Holding Company for Industries and Investment, Ezz Industrial Group (the parent company), which contributes directly and indirectly to the company's capital 65.36%. The company's nominal shares are traded on the Stock Exchange and the London Stock Exchange.

2. Subsidiaries

- Al-Ezz Rolling Mills Company (formerly Al-Ezz Steel Factory) LLC, was established in 1986 according to the provisions of Law 43 of 1974 and replaced by Law 8 of 1997 (actual capacity of 500 thousand tons of reinforcing iron annually, 1.90 million tons of reduced iron under construction in Ain Sukhna.
- Al-Ezz Dekheila Steel Company - Alexandria (LLC) was established in 1982 as a joint investment company in accordance with the provisions of Law 43 of 1974, which was replaced by Law No. 8 of 1997 (actual capacity of 2 million tons of reinforcing iron, 1 million tons of flat steel annually).
- Al Ezz Flat Steel Industry (formerly Al Ezz Heavy Industries LLC) was established in 1998 according to Law 8 of 1997 regarding investment guarantees and incentives (actual capacity 1.3 million tons of flat steel, 1.2 million tons of reinforcing steel).
- Hadid Company for Industry, Trade and Contracting (Contra Steel) LLC the Company was established in accordance with the approval of the competent committee of the Ministry of Economy and Foreign Trade (Companies Department) in accordance with the provisions of Law 159 of 1981.

- Misr Pipe Fittings and Castings Company (SAE) the Company was established in accordance with the provisions of Law 159 of 1981 on August 29, 1992.

3. The Purpose Of The Company And Its Subsidiaries:

The purpose of the company and its subsidiaries is to manufacture, trade and distribute iron and steel of all kinds and related products and services.

The following is a statement of the percentage of investments in the subsidiaries of Ezz Steel, which were included in the consolidated financial statements for the year 2020 (contribution percentage):

- Al-Ezz Rolling Mills 98.91%
- Al Ezz Dekheila Steel Alexandria 54.59%
- Al Ezz Flat Steel Industry 71.07% (direct and indirect through Ezz Dekheila)
- Hadid for Industry, Trade and Contracting 49.13% (indirectly through Ezz Dekheila) (Contrasteel).
- Misr for the manufacture of pipes and castings supplies 47.49% indirectly through Ezz El Dekheila.

Table 1: Company sales, profit and loss during 2019/2020

Statement	2020	2019
Sales Reached During Periods	41.741.880	23.189.275
Sales Cost	37.406.751	20.676.787
Total Profit	4.335.129	2.512.488

The company achieved a net profit/loss as follows: (1,097.164) 560.153.

It is distributed as follows:

Table 2: Company loss/profit during 2019/2020

Share of the company's shareholders	(1.580.207)	162.463
Rights do not control	483.143	397.690
Net Loss/Profit	(1.097.164)	560.153
Principal and reduced share	(2.96)	0.30

Per share in net loss/profit for the year (pounds/shares).

Here it is clear that the company made losses for the year 2020 amounting to (1097164) thousand pounds, compared to the year 2019, where it achieved a profit of 560,153 thousand pounds.

It is also clear that the share incurred losses in the amount of (2.96) pounds per share for 2020, in return it made a profit from 2019 of 0.30 piasters per share.

While the selling and marketing expenses for the year 2020 amounted to 287,251 thousand pounds, an increase in 2006 of 193,806 thousand pounds, but the company achieved losses from 2020, as it is clear, with an amount of 1,097,164 thousand pounds.

Field Study: The researchers conducted personal interviews for a sample of 45 for a number of dealers with Ezz Steel Company in order to get acquainted with the reality of monopoly in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel.

The framework of the interview revolved around the following questions:

Q1-: Are you provided with specific and useful information about the product through the advertisement?

Q2-: Is your personal selling process done as clients by the company?

Q3-: Are widespread media channels used in the publishing process as a tool of the promotional mix?

Q4-: Are you being attracted as new customers to the company through the company's activation of sales as a tool of the promotional mix?

The answers to the previous questions and the results of the interviews with clients were as follows:

1. 85% of the sample answered that we are provided with specific and useful information about the product through advertisements.
2. 83% of the sample answered that our personal sale is done through the presented offer and the prices announced in the newspapers through distribution agents.
3. 95% of the sample answered that the company advertises its product in widely distributed channels.
4. 93% of the sample answered that Ezz Steel is distinguished by its quality and leads to attracting new customers by stimulating sales.

4. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are to evaluate the elements of the promotional mix in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel:

1. Identifying the level of the promotional mix's role in perceiving customers towards Ezz Steel.
2. Reaching some conclusions and recommendations that limit the dominance, control, and monopoly of Ezz Steel, and move towards obtaining greater percentages in the Egyptian market through the promotional mix.

5. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The aspects of the study's importance can be identified from the contribution and expected addition from it, as follows:

1. The study is concerned with studying the effect of the promotional mix on customers.
2. The study is concerned with identifying the elements of the promotional mix.
3. The study is concerned with the quality of the promotional mix offered to customers.

6. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

The scope of the study shall be as follows:

1. **Objective Limits:** The study focused on studying the reality of the promotional mix in Ezz Steel Company for Iron and Steel.

2. **Human Limit:** Customers (steel dealers and agents) in the Canal and Sinai region in Egypt.
3. **Time Limits:** This study was implemented in 2021.
4. **Spatial Limits:** This study was applied to Ezz Steel companies - Egypt.

7. PREVIOUS STUDIES

- Study of (AbdElaal et al., 2021) aimed to identify the dominance and monopoly of Ezz Steel on steel companies in Egypt to obtain a greater percentage in the Egyptian market. And reaching some conclusions and recommendations that limit the dominance, control and monopoly of Ezz Steel Company. The study adopted the descriptive analytical method. The study population consists of customers (steel dealers and agents) in the Canal and Sinai region in Egypt. The results of this study showed the importance of the state's role in setting laws to protect competition, prevent monopolistic practices, and set controls to protect customers. The study presented a set of recommendations, the most important of which are: The necessity of adhering to the provisions of Law No. 3 of 2005 regarding the protection of competition and the prevention of monopoly and the identification of strategic industrial sectors to reduce the impact of monopolistic practices of major industrial companies to prevent monopoly. The importance of setting effective controls for the process of merger and acquisition among public monopoly projects so that the monopoly does not shift from the public sector to the private sector. The necessity of monitoring and directing privatized companies not to establish any monopolistic entity.
- Study of (Bashir, 2015), which aimed to identify the general framework. To promote in the company and stand on the importance of promotion. To identify the relationship between increasing insurance sales and following appropriate promotional methods. This study concluded that the study showed that one of the most important obstacles that may limit the promotional activity of the company comes from the absence of a specialized department for promotion, the lack of qualified cadres and some legal aspects of the inadmissibility of insurance from a jurisprudential point of view. The study showed that the most important promotion methods currently used in the company come in the forefront of public relations and marketing, and then advertising and personal selling. The study showed that the quality of service provided by the company is the most important factor for the success of the company's promotional activity by increasing insurance sales.
- Study of (Abu Khattala and Zargoun, 2015), which aimed to highlight the extent to which the dimensions of industrial development and the advancement of the industrial sector are achieved through the economic policies followed in Algeria in the field of iron and steel industry and its developmental effects on the national economy. This study found the need to realize the importance of the iron and steel industry in the national economy, due to its ability to influence the various sectors and the composition of the added value of its economy to achieve its dependence on oil and achieve sustainable industrial development.
- Study of (Rabie, 2012) which aimed to identify the effect of the sales promotion program used by the institution on the purchasing decision of the final consumer. This study concluded that there is a positive utilitarian impact of the sales activation program on the behavior of the final consumer, through his making the purchase decision and his contribution to raising the sales of the institution. The study recommended that the institution has a great opportunity to be able to create promotional offers, if it tries to get closer to the customer by knowing his purchasing motives, exploiting them and evaluating their results using the most accurate standards to reach the required effectiveness.
- Study of (Abu Amira, 2011) entitled "The Reality of Promotional Practices of Insurance Companies in Gaza Strip and its Impact on Customer Satisfaction". This study aimed to identify the reality of promotional practices in insurance companies. Measure customer satisfaction with user promotional practices and try to increase their satisfaction. This study concluded that customers should be divided into the categories of choosing the most appropriate promotional mix for each category. And make a field increase for customers in the possibility of their presence or survey their opinions about their satisfaction with the services provided and the promotional practices used to increase the level of customer satisfaction.
- Study of (Majid, 2011) that aimed to examine the relationship of electronic promotion to market share and its relationship to gender, marital status, age, job, and type of bank, and further to that, a questionnaire was prepared and distributed to a stratified random sample consisting of 103 bank employees in the northern West Bank. Western. This study found a positive relationship between advertising, public relations, sales activation through electronic promotional means, and market share. The study also found differences in market share in favor of the age group (less than 30 years), as well as differences in electronic promotion and market share in favor of Palestinian banks. Origin (national banks). The study recommended that banks contract with Internet companies or electronic promotion companies to conduct electronic promotional campaigns that can reach all citizens in order to activate sales and increase the number of customers.

- Study of (Al-Issa, 2010), which aimed to evaluate the propaganda method on the behavior of the Iraqi consumer. Clarifying its compatibility with society's technology. The field survey relied on consumer trends, and the sample reached 100 respondents. This study concluded that advertising has a positive effect on the behavior of the Iraqi consumer and its consistency with the culture of society. Emphasis on the need to re-design the advertising advertisement in order to instill confidence in the consumer. The study indicated the need to conduct in-depth studies to understand the behavior of the Iraqi consumer and realize his needs to overcome the shortcomings in advertising to increase the effectiveness of advertising for the consumer.
- Study of (Hussein, 2010) which aimed at the importance of promotion under conditions of intense competition. The AMC Group uses a number of methods. It depends on advertising, in addition to stimulating sales and participating in trade fairs, which give it opportunities to introduce its products, get to know competitors and the quality of their products, and it uses many commercial publications. It is of high quality. AMC has realized the importance of promoting on the Internet and is also concerned with the competitive environment. It collects information about its competitors and analyzes it periodically and continuously. It depends on the competitive distinctive quality standard and on the strategy of excellence to face competition for obtaining the ISO certificate (ISO 9001 2000). This study concluded that it depends on an effective promotional mix that helps the organization improve its competitive position. Its reliance on an effective promotional strategy that is integrated and consistent with the marketing mix strategies and supports it over competition. Creating unconventional promotional ideas and paying attention to quality.
- Study of (Al Murad, 2009), which aimed to benefit from the science of marketing, especially the marketing mix, in marketing services, information and libraries to beneficiaries, and shows the importance of the library in that it provides its services and information to all segments of society. The study concluded that libraries should turn to the principles and techniques of modern marketing, especially the promotional mix, to create and run a documentation system and to overcome problems. Libraries should diversify the means of promotion to achieve the objectives of the library. Benefit from global efforts and ideas for marketing, such as media, advertising, publishing, as well as public signs.
- Study of (Busse, 2002) in which he ensured the subject of strategic cooperation in pricing the cellular industry. It has touched on strategic cooperation in the field of setting prices for the cellular phone industry,

as the researchers explained that the theoretical and experimental study showed that communication between markets may enable them to cooperate and then return their prices and profits despite the apparent difficulty in identifying and explaining the mechanism and mechanics that achieve this cooperation.

- Study of (Liu Chu Mei. 2002) conducted on 800 Filipino subscribers with the aim of studying the effect of the promotional activities of the mobile phone service provider and phone filters on consumer decisions in choosing a business relationship. The results of the study concluded that information bulletins about the service provider and the degree of flexibility in use were among the most important factors influencing the choice of the brand.

Commenting On Previous Studies

- Many previous studies, such as the study (Al Murad, 2008), emphasized the importance of customer satisfaction and their behavioral trends on the presence of a strong influence of the promotional mix elements to express their satisfaction with the services provided, and a study (Abu Amira, 2011) the need to rationalize the decision-making process and conduct field visits For customers to choose the most appropriate promotional mix for each category.
- A study (Busse 2002) agreed. (Liu Chu. Mei 2002) The factors influencing the decision to choose the type of product and the service provider are the most important in the selection process and the necessity of communication and cooperation between markets and cooperation between them.

8. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Promotion: The use of the term promotion has increased in recent times and its definition has varied, as a group of its acquaintances can be monitored, which can be displayed as follows:

- The word promotion is derived from the word to promote something, i.e. known by it, and this means that promotion is to communicate with others and inform them of the types of goods and services that the seller has (Al-Ta'i et al., 2007, P: 207-209).
- Promotion is also defined as coordinating the efforts of the seller in the list of information outlets in facilitating the sale of a good or service or in accepting a particular idea (Al-Alaq and Rabay'ah, 2007, P: 6).
- Promotion also refers to contact with individuals, groups or organizations with the aim of facilitating the exchange of information and persuading the public to accept a particular idea (Abdel-Sabour, 2001, P: 15).
- Also, it is all the planned efforts made by the seller to establish communication channels with consumers to convince them to buy goods or services or promote an idea and promotion is the process and the communication function of marketing El (Bakry, 2007, P: 33).

The most comprehensive definition of promotion is Kotler's definition of promotion as the activity that takes place within the framework of any marketing effort and involves a process of persuasion communication (Al-Ta'i et al., 2007, P: 289).

From the foregoing, it can be concluded that promotion is every activity practiced by the institution in order to contact consumers by introducing it to the types of goods and services available to it and trying to persuade them to buy the product. And that promotion is one of the elements of the marketing mix where the promotional activity cannot be dispensed with to achieve the marketing objectives.

The Importance Of Promotion: It is known in our contemporary world that new products appear in the market quickly, continuously and in a huge amount, and this requires carrying out the promotional activity that facilitates the task of communication between the seller and the buyer, and therefore the importance of promotion can be shown through the following elements (Al-Hajj et al. , 2010):

- Diversity and increase in the number of individuals with whom the product is connected, as the product relates to consumers in addition to commercial intermediaries such as wholesale or retail traders, and the form of communication varies as to whether the market is consumer goods, industrial goods or services.
- It also allows the promotion of hostage-taking and fixing one's feet in this market in the event of intense competition in the market.
- Promotion contributes to maintaining the level of awareness of the development in the lives of individuals, through what it gives him of information and data on everything related to goods or services.
- The organization, through promotional activity, leads to reaching a high level of sales, and this will eventually lead to a reduction in the cost of the unit produced and thus reduce prices by distributing fixed costs over a large number of units produced.
- The amounts allocated to cover the promotional activity are considered the largest allocations in the marketing activity, but it comes in second place after production costs.
- It affects when a person enters a store, for example, we see that he buys other goods in addition to what he planned before entering the store, and this is due to the effects of promotional efforts.

Promotion Budget: Institutions vary in the method of determining the promotion budget. In general, there are four methods used to determine the promotion budget, which we mention after defining the promotion budget, which is defined as the amount of money allocated to spend on promotional elements and advertising means (Al-Hajj et al., 2010, P: 165).

Elements Of The Promotional Mix: The term promotional mix refers to a group of components that interact and integrate with them to achieve the promotional goals of the organization, as the promotional mix is a set of tools used by marketing to find channels of communication between the market and the target audience, the events of the desired

effect, and the promotional mix consists (a mixture of Marketing communication) from a group of components in which each of these elements plays a different role from the role played by the other element, but they integrate with each other to achieve important goals in marketing. The objectives to be achieved, and the selection of any element depends on the following:

- Promotion budget.
- Stages of the life cycle of a good or service.
- The degree of competition in the market.
- The number of products offered by the enterprise.
- The nature of the client.

First: Advertising: The definition of the American Marketing Association is that it is a non-personal means of presenting ideas, goods or services by a known entity and for a fee paid (Al-Alaq and Rabay'ah, 2007, P: 37). Advertising is one of the main elements of the promotional mix and is distinguished from others by the following (Al-Ta'i et al., 2007, P: 299):

- It is a non-personal effort, meaning that the communication between the advertiser and the public is done in an indirect way. This is done using various advertising means such as newspapers, magazines, radio and television. Thus, it differs from personal selling, which is advertised for advertising, which may not be paid for in advertising. It is not limited to displaying and promoting goods and services only, because includes promotion of ideas.
- The advertisement discloses the personality of the advertiser by paying for the advertisement. This differs from advertisement in determining the source of the information. In many cases and cases, the source of the information is not specified in advertisements.

Second: Types Of Advertising: Advertising can be divided into different types according to the marketing functions of the advertisement as follows:

- Educational advertisement this type of advertisement is used to enter the market with new products and aims to educate the consumer on how to use these products and what are their characteristics and advantages.
- Remembrance advertising the purpose of this type of advertisement is to remind the consumer of the advantages of the product, as well as to enhance the position of that product with the consumer.
- Advertising and media (experimental) this type of advertisement aims to make a product famous
- Comparative advertising aims to show the characteristics and advantages compared to other competing products.

Advertising Is Divided According To The Marketing Distribution Channels into (Ali, 2004):

- National or public advertisement The subject of the advertisement here is a product on a national level in general and has consumers all over the country
- Local advertisement (retail advertisement) This advertisement relates to products that are distributed in certain areas only and are limited

- An industrial or technical advertisement, in which the advertisement for production goods that are sold to other producers to be used for production purposes
- Commercial advertisement: It relates to products that are sold to buyers whose goal is to resell again to achieve profits
- Occupational advertising: This type is now related to serving the owners of the same profession by providing information about goods that they do not use themselves, but they recommend to buy and use.

Third: The Foundations on Which the Advertisement Is Based:

The declaration must be based on the following (Ali, 2004, P: 136):

- Determine the target sector or sectors
- Choose the advertising medium
- Selection of advertising content.

Therefore, defining the target sector is an important step and a cornerstone for the success of the rest of the steps, as the choice of the advertising medium depends on an appropriate extent for the target sector. The design of the successful advertising message is also based on the precise identification of the target sector. Despite the importance of clear identification, the importance of advertising messages to the process of introducing the product and its characteristics and advantages for the products which does not have the flexibility of the consumer.

Also, the advertising message should be available on the opinions of a group of customers who have already bought the product, which confirms its advantages, especially if there are some opinion leaders in the group, as a way to accept the perceived degree of risk that the consumer feels from here. For the market and for the advertiser to evaluate the characteristics of the target sector so that the advertising message is designed and the advertising medium selected for the occasion. From this, it can be said that advertising affects the attitudes of individuals (knowledge, emotional and behavior) through a set of intermediate variables that include motivation, ability, level of association with the product, then influence on trends It affects the purchasing behavior of the consumer.

Second: Personal Selling:

Personal selling is defined as a personal communication of information with the aim of persuading a prospective customer to purchase a product, service or idea (Ali, 2004, P: 144).

Personal selling is also defined as the process of information related to the consumer to entice or persuade him to buy a good or service through personal contact in a reciprocal situation (Al-Ta'i et al., 2007, P: 321).

Personal selling is defined as: the personal communication of informing and persuading a potential consumer to buy a good, an idea, or anything that can satisfy his needs or satisfy him.

It is also a two-way method of communication between the seller and the buyer and directly to achieve the appropriate effect on the individual or target group of the sales process (Al-Bakry, 2009, P: 254).

There are duties that a man must fulfill in his promotional and professional field, which are (Al-Bakry, 2009, P: 259):

1. Searching for the potential consumer who is expected to make the purchase.
2. Determine the appropriate manner and timing of reaching the consumer.
3. Using all available skills in marketing communications to inform the consumer about the products and services of the institution and any other information he needs to help him make a purchase decision.
4. Cooperating with the Marketing and Marketing Intelligence Department in collecting and presenting information in accordance with the requirements of their marketing work.

Personal Selling Skills: Although the salesman is originally a conversation with the potential customer to motivate him and encourage him to buy, his ability and skills in listening are the real key to the accuracy of the response in determining the needs of the consumer. As follows (Al-Bakry, 2009, P: 262):

- Conversational skills: represented in his ability to formulate phrases, good pronunciation, and knowing when to be and when to listen
- Experience: It is the total knowledge and information that he possesses about the product he deals with and the institution in which he works
- Communication: to have a clear ability and ease of communication with the potential customer to motivate him and push him to buy
- Responsibility: He must have a clear ability to take responsibility for the work and respond to the exceptional work requirements that may occur
- Participation: where the salesman is part of an integrated sales team, and bears in mind the responsibility of joint work as a basis for the success of the sales work.

From the above, sales activities related to personal selling differ from one person to another or from one institution to another.

Third: Sales Promotion: The process of stimulating sales of the product is an added value directed at facilitating or motivating its use, purchase or distribution. If the purpose is directed to consumers, we are talking here on stimulating sales to consumers, and if it is directed at distributors, we say here activating sales (Lendervie and Lindons, 1997, P: 383). Sales promotion is a term that carries both the techniques and means of communication developed in order to implement a business plan for an organization in order to arouse the intended goal of creating or changing buying or consuming behavior in the short or long term (Jeam, 2002, pL:445). The American Marketing Association defined sales promotion as

a group of marketing activities other than personal selling and advertising, which elicit purchasing behavior and include various presentation methods such as presentation duties, salons, exhibitions, and other sales efforts and activities that go beyond the normal routine (Alexander, 1994, PP: 244-245). . As defined by (Kotler, 1997, p: 661), it is those various things that contain a set of stimulating tools, which are now designed to have a quick and short-term effect for the purpose of accelerating the realization of the purchase of goods or services by the consumer or the merchant.

Fourth: Publication and Public Relations:

A. **Publishing (Advertising):** Publishing is a non-paid activity by luring an editor, broadcaster, or program presenter to conduct a journalistic investigation or publish news in an article or within the newspaper about the institution. Therefore, publication must be on the name of this party in order to publish this news and that it has importance and attractiveness to public opinion. In this case, publication has a large area and is not available for advertising when used, but advertising is distinguished from publication in the possibility of repeating the advertising message according to the advertiser's need, and this is what I do not have a user to publish (Al-Sahn 2001, P: 331).

B. **Public Relations:** It is a consistent, intentional and planned effort to establish and maintain mutual understanding between an organization and its clients (Adcoch Dennis et al, 2001, p: 333). It is also known as a planned program of policies and behavior models that aim to build and support the republic's confidence in the institution and increase mutual understanding between the two parties and seek to understand the behavior of the public and elicit its opinions and notify it of the institution's interest in these trends and desires and work to win the customer's satisfaction on the basis and permanent rules of friendliness and friendship and cooperation (Suwaidan and Haddad, 2003, P: 342).

9. METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURES:

The researchers address the study population and sample, analyze the data, and test the study's hypotheses by answering the questions of the study. A review of the most prominent results of the survey, which was reached by analyzing its expressions. Stand on the variables of the study; Statistical data processing was carried out using statistical packages (SPSS) programs to obtain the results of the study that will be presented and analyzed. Therefore, the researchers first dealt with the population and sample of the study and the descriptive statistics of the results of the field study.

Study Population and Sampling:

The applied study is conducted on the customers of Ezz Steel Company, and accordingly the research community is represented in the total customers in the Canal and Sinai region on 1000 items (iron dealers and agents) in the Canal and Sinai region.

Research Instrument

In order to complete the field study, the researchers designed a survey list of study variables, to be used in collecting data from their primary sources. The researchers selected the study sample according to the tables of random numbers, and it was (278) single (Bazara, 1996, P: 187), and after the researchers exclude the incorrect responses to obtain answers, the results can be generalized.

The sample size reached (250) individuals with a response rate of (89.9%), which is a very acceptable percentage in the social sciences. The researchers relied on the stratified sample method, for two reasons: (the existence of a complete and not obsolete framework with the names of the study sample items, and the existence of a heterogeneous society of the study sample).

10. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics for the Results of the Field Study:

1. Analysis Of Ad Phrases:

Table 3: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of advertising

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company follows modern methods in promoting its services through advertisements on the Internet, satellite stations, posters and publications.	3.37	0.578	%67.37	2
2.	Al Hadid Company presents its advertising campaigns correctly in terms of its type, size, timing, location, and the area to be directed and delivered to.	3.63	0.674	%76.71	1
3.	The company's advertisements focus on the benefits and non-monopoly that the customer seeks to obtain without a monopoly from the company	3.19	0.543	%63.83	3
Overall Average		3.39	0.598	%68.30	

Source: Prepared by researchers.

It is clear from the previous table that the total degree of the responses of the study sample members to the phrases related to advertising was medium, with an arithmetic average of (3.39), and the highest answer for the phrase that states (the iron company presents its advertising campaigns correctly in

terms of its type, size, timing, location and desired area Directing and delivering the advertisement to it) with an arithmetic average of (3.63), while the lowest sample answers came to the statement that states (the company's advertisements focus on the benefits and non-monopoly that

the customer seeks to obtain without monopoly from the company) where the arithmetic average reached (3.19).

2. Analyzing Personal Selling Phrases.

Table 4: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of personal selling

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company is working to attract talented and distinguished and innovative individuals to employ them in the personal selling business.	3.52	0.489	%70.10	2
2.	The good behavior of the salesman or agents encourages customers to continue dealing with the company.	3.4	0.491	%68.05	3
3.	The salesman's skill contributes to attracting new customers.	3.63	0.484	%71.44	1
Overall Average		3.51	0.488	%69.86	

Source: Prepared by researchers.

It is clear from the previous table that the total degree of the responses of the study sample to the phrases related to personal selling was medium, with an arithmetic mean of (3.51), and the highest answer for the phrase that states (the salesman's skill contributes to attracting new customers), where its arithmetic average reached (3.63) in When the least

answers of the sample members came to the statement that (the good treatment of the salesman or agents encourages customers to continue to deal with the company), its arithmetic average was (3.40).

3. Analysis of Sales Promotion Phrases.

Table 5: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of activating sales

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company offers new offers and discounts on its merchandise continuously and appropriately.	3.79	0.638	%76.56	2
2.	I get gifts from the company (discounts).	4.11	0.461	%83.23	1
3.	The company is working to innovate in stimulating sales through offers, prizes and discounts.	3.39	0.834	%70.79	3
Overall Average		3.76	0.644	%76.86	

Source: Prepared by researchers.

It is clear from the previous table that the total degree of answers of the study sample members to the phrases related to sales activation was medium, with an arithmetic mean of (3.76), and the highest answer for the phrase that states (I get gifts (discounts) from the company) came with an arithmetic average of (4.11), While the least answers of the sample

members came to the statement that states (the company is working on innovation in stimulating sales through offers, prizes and discounts), with an arithmetic average of (3.39).

4. Analyzing Publicity and publication Phrases

Table 6: Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and the relative importance of advertising and publishing

#	Item	SMA	Standard Deviation	Relative Importance	Ranking
1.	The company contributes to helping the afflicted and the affected.	3.67	0.459	%76.21	3
2.	The company is working on inventing new types of iron that can withstand erosion factors.	3.98	0.493	%82.57	1
3.	The company contributes to addressing social problems such as damaged homes and the construction of schools and places of worship.	3.71	0.478	%77.10	2
Overall Average		3.78	0.476	%78.64	

Source: Prepared by researchers.

It is clear from the previous table that the total degree of the responses of the study sample members to the phrases related to advertising and publication was medium, where the arithmetic mean was (3.38), and the highest answer was for the phrase that states that (the company is working on creating new types of iron that withstand erosion factors), where its arithmetic average reached (3.98), while the least answers of the sample members came to the phrase that states that (the company contributes to helping the afflicted and the afflicted), with an arithmetic average of (3.67).

11. CONCLUSIONS

The following Results and recommendations were reached:

- The advertising field got a high score with a relative weight (68.3%).
- The field of personal selling got a high score with a relative weight (69.86%).
- The field of sales activation got a high degree with a relative weight (76.86%).

- The field of publicity and publication got a high degree with a relative weight (78.64%).

12. RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings, there are a set of recommendations, as follows:

- The need to enhance the concept of the promotional mix with its various elements (advertising, personal selling, sales promotion, publicity and publication) in order to reduce the impact of monopoly on customers in Ezz Steel.
- Monitoring and directing privatized companies not to establish any monopolistic entity and promoting the concept of the promotional mix among their clients.

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